

MindMentor

IT'S OK NOT TO BE OKAY ALL TIME

Kenfack , Yvan
14 years old
Secondary School

Always face bullying and mockery at school

Leading to Sadness and Isolation

He struggles with low self-esteem and a negative self-image

All this caused him to withdraw socially and affected his studies

Percentage of youth affected by Mental health

World Populations

Total Population is approximately:
8billions

16%

Country with the highest youth population

India

Total Population is approximately: 1.41 billion

40%

African Populations

Total Population is approximately:
1.28 billions

60%

Cameroon Populations

Total Population is approximately:
8 millions

32%

Source: <http://www.unesco.org>

MindMentor

AI enable mental health counsellor application

Freely express feelings and problem through chatbot.

Meet psychologist incase of severe mental health issue

Daily activities according to the mental problem

Peer to Peer Assistance

Daily positive messages

HOW

Technologies

Mobile Application

Computer vision

Data Analysis by the AI

Store information in the cloud

Voice Recognition

Proposed appropriate solutions

Satisfied Patient

Existing solutions

	MIND. MENTO R	MURRO R	NOBU	WYSA	YOUPE R
Vocal assistant	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Chat box	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Anonymo us	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Exchange of experienc es	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Facial expressio n detector	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Contact a specialiste					

Mind.Mentor

Desktop View

Mobile View

AI Support Page

Peer to Peer Assistance page

Contact PSY Page

Thank For You Keen Attention

We are opened to questions

**NOUPOUWO
STEPHANE**

Team Presentator

**DJOUMESSI
WENDY**

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**LONTOUO
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